

$R(M^{2,-1}, 2)$ LEYBNITS ALGEBRASINING DIFFERENSIALLASHI VA TO'LIQLIGI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada $R(M^{-2,-1}, 2)$ differenziallashi va to'liqligi tekshirilgan

Kalit so'zlar: nilpotent, differenziallash, yechiluvchanlik, ideal, markaz

Ta'rif 1. F maydon ustida aniqlangan G algebraning ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlari uchun quyidagi ayniyatlar bajarilsa,

$$[x, x] = 0 - \text{antikommutativlik ayniyati,}$$

$$[[x, y], z] + [[y, z], x] + [[z, x], y] = 0 - \text{Yakobi ayniyati}$$

G algebra Li algebrasi deyiladi, bu yerda $[-, -]$ – G algebrada aniqlangan ko'paytirish amali.

Ta'rif 2. maydon ustida aniqlangan L algebraning ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlari uchun quyidagi Leybnis ayniyati bajarilsa

$$[x, [y, z]] = [[x, y], z] - [[x, z], y],$$

L algebra Leybnist algebrasi deyiladi, bu yerda $[-, -]$ – L da aniqlangan ko'paytirish amali.

Ixtiyoriy L Leybnist algebrasi uchun quyidagi quyi markaziy va hosilaviy ketma-ketliklarni mos ravishda aniqlaymiz:

$$L^1 = L, \quad L^{k+1} = [L^k, L^1]; \quad L^{[1]} = L, \quad L^{[k+1]} = [L^{[k]}, L^{[k]}], \quad k \geq 1.$$

Ta'rif 3. L Leybnist algebrasi uchun shunday $s \in \mathbb{N}$ son mavjud bo'lib, $L^{[s]} = 0$ (mos ravishda, $L^s = 0$) bo'lsa, u holda L yechiluvchan (mos ravishda, nilpotent) Leybnist algebrasi deyiladi.

Ixtiyoriy Leybnist algebrasining maksimal nilpotent ideali uning nilradikali deyiladi.

Ta'rif 4. Aytaylik $L - n$ -o'lchamli Leybnist algebrasi bo'lsin. Agar uning nilindeksi $n-1$ ga teng bo'lsa, u holda L kvazi-filiform Leybnist algebrasi deyiladi.

Aytaylik $L - n$ olga teng bo'lmagan fazolarning chekli soni bilan Z -graduirlangan Leybnist algebrasi, ya'ni $L = \bigoplus_{i \in Z} V_i$ bo'lsin, bu yerda har qanday $i, j \in Z$ lar uchun $[V_i, V_j] \subseteq V_{i+j}$.

L nilpotent Leybnist algebrasi, agar $L = V_{k_1} \oplus V_{k_2} \oplus \dots \oplus V_{k_t}$ bo'lsa, bu yerda barcha i ($k_1 \leq i \leq k_t$) lar uchun $V_i \neq 0$, bog'langan graduirovkani qabul qiladi deymiz.

$len(\oplus L) = k_1 - k_1 + 1$ soni graduirovkaning uzunligi deyiladi. Keyinchalik, $l(L) = \max \{len(\oplus L) = k_1 - k_1 + 1 \mid L = V_{k_1} \oplus V_{k_2} \oplus \dots \oplus V_{k_t} \text{ bog'langan graduirovka}\}$ ni L Leybnist algebrasining uzunligi deb ataymiz.

Ta'rif 5. L Leybnist algebrasi, agar $l(L) = \dim L$ bo'lsa, maksimal uzunlikdagi algebra deyiladi.

Teorema[2]. Maksimal uzunlikdagi har qanday n -o'lchamli ($n \geq 6$) kvazi-filiform Li bo'lmagan Leybnist algebrasi quyidagi o'zaro izomorf bo'lmagan algebra oilalaridan biriga izomorfdir:

$$M^{1,\delta} : \begin{cases} [e_1, e_1] = e_n, & [e_{n-1}, e_1] = e_2, [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 2 \leq i \leq n-3, \\ [e_{n-1}, e_{n-1}] = \delta e_4, \delta \in \{0, 1\}, & [e_i, e_{n-1}] = \delta e_{3+i}, & 2 \leq i \leq n-5; \end{cases}$$

Bu yerda $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ algebraning bazisi.

Ta'rif 6. Aytaylik $d - L$ Leybnist algebrasining chiziqli almashtirishi bo'lsin. Agar ixtiyoriy $x, y \in L$ lar uchun quyidagi tenglik bajrilsa

$$d([x, y]) = [d(x), y] + [x, d(y)],$$

u holda d chiziqli almashtirishga L Leybnist algebrasining differensiallashi deyiladi.

Ta'kidlab o'tamizki, algebra elementiga o'ngdan ko'paytirish operatorlari (ya'ni, algebraning har qanday y elementi uchun $\mathcal{R}_x(y) = [x, y]$) differensiallash bo'ladi, biz ularni ichki differensiallashlar deb ataymiz.

Ta'rif 7. L - Leybnist algebrasi bo'lsin, $Center(L) = \{x \in L \mid [x, L] = [L, x] = 0\}$ L ga algebraning markazi deyiladi..

Ta'rif 8. L Leybnist algebrasi to'liq deyiladi, agar uning markazi nol(trivial) va har qanday differensiallashi ichki bo'lsa.

Teorema[1]. R -nilradikali $M^{-2,1}$ va $dim Q = 2$ ga teng bo'lgan yechiluvchan Leybnist algebrasi bo'lsin, u holda R quyidagi algebra izomorf bo'ladi:

$$R(M^{-2,1}, 2) : \begin{cases} [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1} & 1 \leq i \leq n-3, \\ [e_i, x_1] = ie_i, & 1 \leq i \leq n-2, \\ [e_n, x_1] = -[x_1, e_n] = e_n, & [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, \\ [e_{n-1}, x_2] = -[x_2, e_{n-1}] = e_{n-1}, \\ [e_n, x_2] = -[x_2, e_n] = e_n \\ [e_{n-1}, e_1] = e_n, \\ [e_1, e_{n-1}] = -e_n \end{cases}$$

Biz $R(M^{-2,1}, 2)$ algebrani differensiallashlarini xisoblab quyidagi tasdiqni olishimiz mumkin..

Tasdiq 4. $R(M^{-2,1}, 2)$ algebraning ixtiyoriy differensiallashi quyidagicha matrisaviy ko'rinishga ega:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & a_{1,n} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 4a_{1,1} & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & a_{2,n-1} & a_{1,2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & a_{2,n-1} + a_{1,1} & 0 & 0 \\ -a_{1,2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & b_{1,n} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & a_{1,n} & b_{1,n} & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Исботи: $d - R(M^{-2,1}, 2)$ algebraning differensiallashi bo'lsin.

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_1) &= \sum_{i=1}^n a_{1,i} e_i + a_{1,n+1} x_1 + a_{1,n+2} x_2, \\ d(e_{n-1}) &= \sum_{i=1}^n a_{2,i} e_i + a_{2,n+1} x_1 + a_{2,n+2} x_2, \\ d(x_1) &= \sum_{i=1}^n b_{1,i} e_i + b_{1,n+1} x_1 + b_{1,n+2} x_2, \\ d(x_2) &= \sum_{i=1}^n b_{2,i} e_i + b_{2,n+1} x_1 + b_{2,n+2} x_2 \end{aligned}$$

Qo'yish mumkin .

$d([e_1, x_1]) = [d(e_1), x_1] + [e_1, d(x_1)]$ dan foydalanib quyidagi chekli tengliklarni olamiz

$$a_{1,i} = b_{1,n+1} = a_{1,n+1} = a_{1,n+2} = 0, b_{1,n-1} = 0, b_{1,1} = -a_{1,2}, 3 \leq i \leq n - 1.$$

Huddi shunday , $d([x_1, e_1])$ va $d([x_1, x_1])$ uchun differensiallash xossasidan foydalanib $b_{1,i} = 0, 2 \leq i \leq n - 2$ яъни

$$d(e_1) = a_{1,1} e_1 + a_{1,2} e_2 + a_{1,n} e_n, d(x_1) = -a_{1,2} e_1 + b_{1,n} e_n + b_{1,n+2} x_2.$$

$$0 = d([x_2, x_1]) = [d(x_2), x_1] + [x_2, d(x_1)] \text{ dan } b_{2,i} = 0, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

$b_{2,n} = b_{1,n}$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

$d([x_1, x_2])$ va $d([x_2, e_1])$ uchun differensiallash xossasidan foydalanib,

$$b_{2,1} = 0 \text{ va } b_{2,n+1} = 0, a_{2,n-1} = a_{1,n} \text{ ni olamiz.}$$

$$d([e_1, e_1]) = [d(e_1), e_1] + [e_1, d(e_1)] \text{ tenglikdan } d(e_2) = 2a_{1,1} e_2 + a_{1,2} e_3.$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

$$d([e_{n-1}, x_2]) = [d(e_{n-1}), x_2] + [e_{n-1}, d(x_2)]$$

tenglikdan

$$a_{2,n+1} = a_{2,n+2} = b_{2,n+2} = 0, a_{2,i} = 0, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \text{ ga ega bo'lamiz.}$$

$d([e_{n-1}, x_1]) = [d(e_{n-1}), x_1] + [e_{n-1}, d(x_1)]$ tenglikdan $a_{2,n} = a_{1,2}$, $b_{1,n+2}=0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Buni induksiya metodi orqali ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Va quyidagigacha natijaga erishamiz .

$$\begin{aligned} d(e_i) &= \left((i)a_{1,1}e_i + a_{1,2} e_{i+1} \right) , 2 \leq i \leq n-3, \\ d(e_{n-2}) &= (n-2)a_{1,1}e_{n-2}. \\ d(e_{n-1}) &= a_{2,n-1}e_{n-1} + a_{1,2}e_n. \\ d(e_n) &= (a_{2,n-1}+a_{1,1})e_n, \quad d(x_1) = -a_{1,2}e_1 + b_{1,n}e_n. \\ d(e_1) &= a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{1,2}e_2 + a_{1,n}e_n, \\ d(x_2) &= a_{1,n}e_{n-1} + b_{1,n}e_n. \end{aligned}$$

Tasdiq isbotlandi

Tasdiq 5. $R(M^{-2,1}, 2)$ Leybnist algebra si to'liqdir

Isboti: $R(M^{-2,1}, 2)$ algebraning markazining nolli gi ko'paytirish jadvalidan bevosita kelib chiqadi. Navbatda $R_{e_1}, R_{x_1}, R_{x_2}, R_{e_{n-1}}, R_{e_n}$ ichki differensiallashlarni hisoblab topamiz

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} R_{e_1}(e_{n-1}) = e_n, \quad R_{e_1}(x_1) = -e_1, \\ R_{e_1}(e_i) = e_{i+1}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-3 \\ R_{x_1}(e_n) = e_n, \quad R_{e_{n-1}}(x_2) = -e_{n-1} \\ R_{x_1}(e_i) = ie_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n-2 \\ R_{x_2}(e_{n-1}) = e_{n-1}, \quad R_{x_2}(e_n) = e_n \\ R_{e_n}(x_2) = -e_n, \quad R_{e_{n-1}}(e_1) = -e_n, \\ R_{e_n}(x_1) = -e_n \end{array} \right.$$

Tasdiq 4 ga ko'ra

$$Der(R(M^{-2,1}, 2)) = a_{1,1}R_{x_1} + a_{1,2}R_{e_1} - a_{1,n}R_{e_{n-1}} + a_{2,n-1}R_{x_2} - b_{1,n}R_{e_n}.$$

Natijada $R(M^{-2,1}, 2)$ algebraning barcha differensiallashlari ichki ekanligi kelib chiqdi.

Tasdiq isbotlandi

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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